

Feedback on the Requirement Elicitation Interview System

Thank you for participating the experiment. Please help us to identify how you evaluate our system by answering the questions below.

* Indicates required question

1. Name Surname *

2. Which system you interviewed with? *

Mark only one oval.

Text to speech client

Robotic client

3. How engaged you were while using this interview system? *

Mark only one oval.

Not engaged at all

1

2

3

4

5

Extremely engaged

4. How helpful did you find the interview system to identify the mistakes in your interview questions? *

Mark only one oval.

Not helpful at all

1

2

3

4

5

Extremely helpful

- 5. Using this interview system would increase my success in learning how to conduct requirement elicitation interviews. *

Mark only one oval.

Extremely disagree

1

2

3

4

5

Extremely agree

- 6. Using this interview system would decrease my overall training time in learning how * to conduct requirement elicitation interviews.

Mark only one oval.

Extremely disagree

1

2

3

4

5

Extremely agree

7. Using this interview system would decrease the number of mistakes in my further requirement elicitation interviews. *

Mark only one oval.

Extremely disagree

1

2

3

4

5

Extremely agree

8. Using this interview system would improve my behavioral skills and interview management capabilities.

*

Mark only one oval.

Extremely disagree

1

2

3

4

5

Extremely agree

9. I would find this interview system useful in requirement elicitation interview trainings. *

Mark only one oval.

Extremely disagree

1

2

3

4

5

Extremely agree

10. Using this interview system is easy for me. *

Mark only one oval.

Extremely disagree

1

2

3

4

5

Extremely agree

11. I felt relaxed enough during the overall interaction. *

Mark only one oval.

Extremely disagree

1

2

3

4

5

Extremely agree

12. I find the interview system easy to follow and manage. *

Mark only one oval.

Extremely disagree

1

2

3

4

5

Extremely agree

13. It would be easy for me to become experienced in conducting requirement elicitation interviews by using this interview system.

*

Mark only one oval.

Extremely disagree

1

2

3

4

5

Extremely agree

14. The interview environment is realistic enough. *

Mark only one oval.

extremely disagree

1

2

3

4

5

extremely agree

15. Rate the practicality of the dialogue options given in the interview system. *

Mark only one oval.

Not practical at all (I wanted to say something completely different)

1

2

3

4

5

Very practical (Exactly what I wanted to say)

16. Rate the effectiveness of the feedback component of the interview system. *

Mark only one oval.

Not effective at all

1

2

3

4

5

Extremely effective

17. Rate the effectiveness of performance analysis provided at the end of the interview.

*

Mark only one oval.

Not effective at all

1

2

3

4

5

Extremely effective

18. Using this interview system makes me feel... *

Mark only one oval.

annoyed

1

2

3

4

5

happy

19. Using this interview system makes me feel... *

Mark only one oval.

negative

1

2

3

4

5

positive

20. Using this interview system makes me feel... *

Mark only one oval.

bad

1

2

3

4

5

good

21. This interview system is a(n) _____ instrument to improve my requirement elicitation interview skills.

*

Mark only one oval.

foolish

1

2

3

4

5

wise

22. This interview system is a(n) _____ instrument to improve my requirement elicitation interview skills.

*

Mark only one oval.

harmful

1

2

3

4

5

beneficial

23. This interview system is a(n) _____ instrument to improve my requirement elicitation interview skills. *

Mark only one oval.

worthless

1

2

3

4

5

valuable

24. On average, I would use this interview tool in my requirement elicitation training *

Mark only one oval.

Not at all

Once

2 or 3 times

More than 3 times

25. What did you like most about this interview system? *

26. What did you like least about this interview system? *

27. Please write recommendations for improving this system, if any

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